

Teaching Multicultural Early Childhood Development (ECD) classes in Zvimba District, Zimbabwe: Successes and Challenges

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ABSTRACT

Globally, the teaching of multicultural classes is a cause of concern where quality education is of utmost importance and should be accessed by all learners regardless of one's culture or ethnic group. In most parts of the Zvimba district, there are Early Childhood Development learners from different communities, and all are found in the same class. Accordingly, this study focused on the teaching of multicultural ECD classes in Zvimba District, looking at successes and challenges in a quest for equity and equal access to quality early childhood education. The literature reviewed the successes and challenges of teaching a multicultural class. Guided by the Social Identity theory, this research paper uses the Interpretivist paradigm, and a qualitative approach to collect data from four ECD teachers who were purposively selected in a single of case research design. The methodological design employed interviews as methods of collecting data. Data gathering was done through interviews with the TICs, and ECD/Infant teachers. The data gathered was analyzed in a descriptive manner. Aspects such as lack of training, confidence, resources, and bias towards one's culture were cited as major barriers in teaching multicultural classes. Purposive sampling was used to select the participants. Data were analyzed by describing respondents' responses to each research question. The major findings of the study were that teachers understood multiculturalism. However, the ECD/Infant teachers' work experience revealed that they lacked multicultural education since their qualifications did not include multicultural education programs. Multicultural classes need multicultural education programs which might be a new phenomenon to ECD/infant teachers. The study recommends that the Ministry of Education reinforce multicultural education training and courses for TiCs and ECD/Infant teachers.

Keywords: Multicultural class, Early Childhood Development, Teaching, Successes, Challenges

Introduction and background

Multiculturalism is a growing movement in many countries (Crocco, 2021). The reason for the growth, especially in academics, is the concern about dealing with cultural minorities respecting human rights (Johansson, 2022). As the population from diverse cultural backgrounds continues to grow, so does the need for teachers to be able to effectively teach and engage with students of all backgrounds. Teaching a multicultural class presents a unique set of challenges and successes (Suri & Chandra, 2021; Csillik, 2022). To understand the successes and challenges associated with teaching a multicultural class, it is important to look at the current literature and research on the subject. Success stories typically focus on the positive outcomes associated with teaching a multicultural class, such as increased student engagement and improved academic performance. From a global perspective multicultural education particularly in European countries like Greece multiculturalism was necessitated by consequence of the Second World War, fast growing technological advancements, the advent of the 4th industrial revolution as well as globalization (Karanikola, Katsioli & Palaiologou, 2022; Papadopoulou, Palaiologou & Karanikola, 2022). As people are

living in the global village so is the education should encompass all learners from diverse cultural backgrounds. Karanikola, Katsioui & Palaiologou (2022) assert that due to increased number of migrants, Greece enacted a law that allows for the establishment of multicultural schools. However, even though teachers were willing to teach some drawbacks were noted in lack of understanding various cultural background of these learners, the language of use. In Asian countries like South Korea, a finding from research by Walton (2021) implies that there were some tensions between reality of diversity and multicultural policy approach that saw minority ethnic learners trying to fit in the major Korean culture. This entails that the minority learners cultural affiliations were somehow not recognized. Banks (2021) opined that to maintain a multicultural school environment, all aspects of the school must be examined and transformed, including policies, teachers' attitudes, instructional materials, assessment methods, counseling, and teaching styles. Ogletree and Lake (2010) state that in the United States of America (USA), the National Association of the Education of Young Children (NAEYC) provides a national accreditation program for childcare centres. On the contrary in Turkey, Alanay and Aydin (2016) aver that teaching multicultural classes had some benefits and challenges, the benefits include the creation of a culture comprising numerous cultures, the increase in communication between cultures, the ability to take advantage of mutual cultural values rather than remaining focused on one source of knowledge or one trend, experiences and practices are obtained from all over the world as well as students abandoning any prejudices and racist thoughts.

The excessive highlighting of cultural differences may lead to situations in which negative reactions are displayed towards cultural differences and students experience condescension because of their cultural experiences (Wee, Karkkulainen & Tateo, 2023). Sharing the same view, Akkari & Radhouane (2022) opine that multicultural education may be seen as a component that has simply been added to existing education programs to placate those of African background, Latinos, Far-east Asians, East Asians, and those of other minority groups. In the context of this study for instance, on the recognizing of the 16 languages as official languages in Zimbabwe, people may get divided along the aspect of language. At school, learners will play in groups of the same language. For example, Zezurus on their own Ndebeles, Nyanjas, and so on. Therefore, this may pose some challenges typically when focusing on the difficulties associated with teaching a multicultural class, such as language barriers, cultural differences, and lack of resources (Ngwenya, 2020; Bhebhe, 2023). In the Northern parts of Zvimba area, the school catchment area is comprised of mining and farming communities. This makes the classes at most schools in that area to be multicultural classes as learners come from different cultures. As such, in the context of this study, those learners from farms will bring in vast knowledge in farming crops and so forth, while those from mining communities will be beneficial when it comes to some dances like Gule Wankulu in the Visual and Performing Arts learning area. Research suggests that successful teaching in a multicultural classroom requires teachers to be aware of and sensitive to the cultural and linguistic diversity of students (Zembere and Madenga, 2023; Chikodzi, 2022). Therefore, teachers in that area are expected to be knowledgeable about their students' cultural backgrounds and be able to create a classroom environment that is respectful of all students' backgrounds. Teachers must also be able to create engaging and effective lesson plans that are tailored to the needs of their students.

Multicultural education is not a task to be done or even an end goal to be accomplished. Instead, Wee, Karkkulainen & Tateo (2023) analyze multicultural education as an approach to education that aims to include all students, promote learning of other cultures, and teach healthy social skills in a multicultural setting. Hence, multicultural classes are composed of learners from diverse cultural backgrounds which they brought to the class. Thondhlana, Chitima & Chirikure (2021) believes that

every teacher in a multicultural classroom should expect to have differences with learners in classroom participation especially if the major language used in the classroom is foreign. This means that language or even a second language to the learner would make the learner not to be very comfortable in classroom participation. Furthermore, language can be a barrier in teaching multicultural classes. According to Ndamba and Madzanire (2022) mother tongue plays a crucial role in creating the capacity for children to access and create knowledge. Therefore, teachers should know the various cultures and the aspects which unite learners. As such the curriculum did not give due attention to local circumstances, particularly accommodating the needs of the learner in terms of cultural diversity.

Ndamba, Sithole and Van Wyk (2017), posits that in cases where different ethnic groups co-exist, all school activities including cultural ones automatically become multicultural. This implies that in Zimbabwe mostly mining areas and former white-owned farming areas are bound to be having learners of varied cultures. In Zimbabwe, for example, multiculturalism and diversity issues are enshrined in the post-independence national cultural and educational policies (Mukwacha, 2020). This implies that multiculturalism is encompassed in the Zimbabwean Education ACT of 1987. Hence the assumption will be that multiculturalism in education is being practiced in the schools but without any policy. The absence of an official policy on multicultural education presents problems in terms of implementation. Thus, the paper study seeks to explore the challenges and successes of teaching multicultural classes in the Zimbabwean primary schools of the Zvimba district.

Research Questions

- i. What aspects of multiculturalism can be encountered in early childhood classes?
- ii. How can ECD multicultural classes be successfully taught in schools?
- iii. Why do educators face challenges when teaching students from multiple cultural backgrounds in a multicultural class?

Theoretical Framework

The study is informed by the Social Identity theory. The Social Identity theory suggests that individuals categorize themselves into groups based on social characteristics such as race, ethnicity, and culture (Verkuyten, 2021). As such, learners are engaged in learning activities chances are high that they may form their groups based on cultural aspects like language, race or colour. Consequently, the theory emphasizes the importance of acknowledging and respecting the various identities present in a multicultural classroom (Reimer, Schmid, Hewstone & Al Ramiah, 2022). Teachers will thus have expected to create a positive, conducive learning environment that encourages learners to share their cultural backgrounds and experiences in a multicultural environment. Based on that assumption, learners from different cultural backgrounds in the classroom form a multicultural class through which the learners will have convergent and divergent ideas as far as knowledge acquisition is concerned. They would need to be oriented to have respect and tolerance towards each other's culture.

Literature Review

Language

Language is viewed by Vygotsky in Lecusay, Anna and Ferholt (2022) as the vehicle of thoughts and a tool for communication. Thus, language is used as a means of transmitting thoughts, information,

and expressions from adults to children. In a multicultural class, learners may be bilingual or multilingual. In such scenarios, it will be an added advantage both to the learner, other learners, and the facilitator, as well as there, will not be a communication barrier as compared to scenarios where a child will be having only one language (Ndamba and Madzanire, 2022). Having one language might pose a lot of problems for learners for example, in Zimbabwe, if a Nyanja speaker is among the Shona speakers he or she feels inferior and his or her language may be belittled by other learners. In the context of this research paper, learners from the Zvimba district speak the following languages Chikaranga, ChiZezuru, Chinyanja, and English. Implementation of the multicultural approach will therefore assist them to appreciate each other.

During the colonial era in Zimbabwe, the Doke Report of the 1930s set the stage for a colonial language policy in education where English was declared the official language and medium of instruction in the education system (Ndhlovu, 2024). This left ChiShona and IsiNdebele to become the only indigenous languages taught in the education system. The two indigenous languages mentioned were not the only languages, but they were referred to as the language of the majority (Ndou, 2021). This, therefore, left out some other languages for the minority groups. Some indigenous minority languages were only later acknowledged after the 1987 Education Act. Though the 1987 Education Act brings joy to some indigenous languages the government also needs to consider those pupils whose mother tongue is not used as a medium of instruction. These pupils whose mother tongue is not taught and recognized in the education system in terms of the 1987 Education Act do not benefit from instruction in the mother tongue and this brings some inequality in accessing quality ECD education. However, to address such an anomaly, the New Constitution of Zimbabwe number 20 Act as amended (2013) Chapter 2 Article 6 officially recognizes sixteen indigenous languages, namely, Chewa, Chibarwe, English, Kalanga, Koisan, Nambya, Ndau, Ndebele, Shangani, Shona, Sign Language, Sotho, Tonga, Tswana, Venda and Xhosa, (Maseko & Ndlovu, 2013). This is a great stride towards equity and equality in ECD education for all learners in the Zvimba district.

Training of Teachers on Bilingualism and Multilingualism.

In the event of a language barrier between learners and teachers, the teacher, if trained in bilingual or multilingual, will find a common ground by using a language of wider communication or just an alternative language for the best interest of the child. Though the GoZ is trying its best to assist in the training of teachers of languages which were considered a minority through the Teacher Capacity Development Programme, there is a need for robust training in all primary school teachers' training colleges so that no one child in a multicultural class will be left out in the curriculum. In the context of this study, the mandate for students at primary school training colleges to have at least two indigenous languages besides English will be a positive move towards bilingualism and multilingualism which will fulfill the government's position of recognition of all indigenous languages. At the university level like Great Zimbabwe University, there are programs in African languages which are indigenous languages such as Xitsonga, Venda, and Xichangana among others.

Importance of Multicultural Education

Cultural differences in society also bring together new challenges in education. According to Salgur (2015) dialogue and peace in societies depend on the training of individuals dealing with education. This leads to acknowledgement that individuals who respect each other and see cultural differences as a fact of life can establish social peace.

Gay (2000) opines various purposes of multicultural education are not limited to including developing ethnic and cultural literacy. In this way, students learn about their own and others' languages, cultural characteristics, critical events, significant individuals, historical backgrounds, and majority and minority ethnic groups.

The Challenges of Multiculturalism

According to Lafer (2014), there have been several negative viewpoints expressed about worries that multicultural education harbors malevolent intentions that serve to increase the distance between different groups and damage the unity and territorial integrity of the nation-states due to the fact of mentioning subcultures in a culture.

According to Lacaste, Ming-Min & Hsueh-Hua Chuang. (2022), the excessive highlighting of cultural differences may lead to situations in which negative reactions are displayed towards cultural differences and students experience condescension because of their cultural experiences. However, Runhare & Mulaudzi (2012) argue that more needs to be done in terms of having textbooks that cut across that for example if it is an IsiNdebele textbook, it should also reflect on what is done in other areas that are non-Ndebele maybe through stories and so on.

Karanikola, Katsioulis & Palaiologou (2022) argues that multiculturalism is temporary and liable to change as it might work either positively or negatively. For example, a context of peaceful and respectful relationships between different groups might not last indefinitely. Hence, what works for the present generation may not work so well in future times, and good government in a multicultural society requires looking ahead to future developments. In the context of this study, if learners differ in language or dressing those aspects may come to pass with time, and globalization or political stance may intervene to dictate what is to be done as a nation, not groups. However, in Zimbabwe, the National Constitution Number 20 Act (2013) is one piece of legislation that came to rectify through recognizing languages from minority ethnic groups as official languages and this is done through education which has an extremely significant role to play in the way in which understanding, toleration for and engagement with diversity and other groups are developed across the national context.

Research Methodology

This research paper was informed by the Phenomenology paradigm which according to Kumatongo & Muzata (2021) is the study of a phenomena, which might be an event, a situations or experiences that people lived in. The goal of phenomenology is to describe experiences as they are lived by participants (Pilarska, 2021). The research paradigm is chosen on the belief that in a multicultural class the participants encountered varied experiences with learners from different cultural background. Hence, the individual experiences bring about unique reality. As a result, these unique realities will bring about what exactly are the success and challenges of teaching in an ECD Multicultural class.

Case study

This study views a case study as an inquiry into analyzing the quality and inclusive education in Zimbabwe focusing on analyzing the teaching of multicultural ECD classes in Zvimba District, Zimbabwe looking at the successes and challenges. Schools in Zvimba District were chosen by virtue of their enrolment catchment areas which is comprised of people of diverse cultural backgrounds.

Population

It is the total number of large collections of individuals or objects with the same characteristics (Creswel & Hirose, 2019). These participants were selected from schools that have learners from diverse cultural backgrounds. The participants in the research will be ECD-qualified teachers at the three selected primary schools.

Sample and Sampling Procedure

In this study, participants were selected based on a purposive sample (non-probability) and thus could not be expected to be representative. Purposive sampling allowed the researcher to focus on characteristics of a population that was of interest (Pace, 2021). This sampling enables the researcher to have the rightful participants who are teaching the required grade level. In this case, three ECD-qualified teachers, one per each of the selected schools. The researcher handpicked the sample thus choosing the teachers who teach ECD where there is more than one ECD teacher the researcher considered seniority.

Data collection

Data was collected using semi-structured interviews. The use of interviews as a technique to solicit data was very important because the researcher managed to operate on a one-on-one basis with the participants (Adeoye-Olatunde, and Olenik, 2021). However, the researcher had the opportunity to probe information further through follow up questions.

Data Analysis Procedure

Khoa, Hung and Hejsalem-Brahmi (2023) state that in concurrent forms of data collection, the analysis is conducted for different purposes such as to converge the findings, to validate one form of data through the other, to transform data for comparisons, and to generate data that will address different types of questions. As such, data was coded first and then put into themes defined categories for analysis.

Discussion of Findings

Despite being at different schools, TIC and ECD teachers were noted to be teaching multicultural classes. In these classes there are some challenges and benefits they encountered from that set up. Participants indicated different views pertaining to successes and challenges of multicultural classes. Responding to interview questions on the aspects of multiculturalism that can be encountered in multicultural ECD classes, the TiCs gave various opinions of what entails multiculturalism in ECD class. Mostly highlighted as aspects of multiculturalism was the difference in cultural background, home language, beliefs, norms, values, traditional games, food, cultural practices, and clothing. Therefore, participants view a multicultural class to be comprised of learners from varied cultural backgrounds whose norms, beliefs and values as well as cultural practices differ or converge at some point. This was indicated by the responses they gave aligned to the research questions as shown below:

What aspects of multiculturalism can be encountered in early childhood classes?

TIC School B has this to say:

In ECD classes, Multiculturalism is an educational act that encompasses teaching and learning about different cultures' ways of living, food, and dressing among other aspects.

Meanwhile TIC **School A** is of the opinion that:

Multiculturalism in ECD classes is an approach that entails the inclusion of multiple cultures' religions and cultural beliefs in the educational system.

TIC **School C** views aspects of multiculturalism focusing on curriculum content. She has this to say:

Multiculturalism includes education and involves interpretation of the syllabus by facilitators which has to do with different cultures.

On the other hand, ECD/Infant teachers as classroom practitioners and implementers of the curriculum have the same perception of Multiculturalism aspects as TIC as noted from their responses below:

ECD/Infant teacher **School A** has this to say:

A multicultural class is the one which is comprised of learners from various cultural backgrounds with different beliefs, practices and values.

ECD/Infant teacher **School B** shared her sentiments on multiculturalism aspects as follows:

Multiculturalism is an approach to inclusive education as far as cultural aspects are concerned. Multiculturalism aspects in ECD implies that all students, regardless of their gender, social class, and ethnic, racial, or cultural characteristics, are given an equal opportunity to learn in school.

ECD/Infant teacher school C has this to say:

Multiculturalism in education is a system that wants to see all the cultures and whole spectrum of cultures being taught to all learners.

As a result, TIC, and infant teachers conceptualize Multiculturalism as an educational approach that considers the teaching and learning of cultures in any given society. Therefore, all the participants who furnished the researcher with information showed that they have knowledge of multiculturalism aspects in education that can enable the teacher and learners to effectively enjoy the benefits of the vast cultural diversity of opinion from various cultures in class. This was so as all the participants brought the issue of bringing diverse cultural aspects into one class. The aspects raised include food, clothing, religion beliefs and values as well as curriculum sensitivity towards various cultures in children's learning. From the interview with the TICs, multicultural education was viewed as an educational act and an approach that takes into consideration other cultures. All the TIC concurred that the diverse cultural experiences brought by learners enriches cultural respect and tolerance in school and society. However, some learners might feel shy of their cultural affiliations. Similarly, to a finding by Lacaste, Ming-Min & Hsueh-Hua Chuang (2022), over emphasis on cultural differences may expose other cultures to be superior to others.

On the question of how can ECD multicultural classes be successfully taught in schools? It was revealed in the study findings that teachers use a variety of strategies in the teaching of multicultural classes. The strategies range from dramatization, games, and engaging resource persons. Further explanation was given from the participants responses as follows:

How can ECD multicultural classes be successfully taught in schools?

TIC **School A** highlighted some strategies used by ECD/Infant teachers to include:

dramatization, field trips, discussions, and devil's advocate whereby learners may be given a topic to move or oppose about multiculturalism.

TIC **School B** suggests that:

Through engagement of resource-persons and research on different cultures, learners grasp a lot of multicultural concepts. More so, by having staff development with facilitators and providing resources like textbooks, thorough supervision of facilitators' day-to-day teaching and learning business

While TIC **School C** believes in the following:

Calling in resource persons, role play, workshops, and demonstration lessons. This will boost self-confidence in the teacher and morale of the learners

ECD /Infant teachers as managers of the ECD classes also highlighted some strategies that can be employed to implement multicultural education in their classes. The strategies were noted as follows:

ECD /Infant teachers **School A** feels a multicultural class can be effectively taught through use of resource- persons and active participation by learners as she had this to say:

Through engaging a resource person, we are rest assured that the learners will get accurate information from the horse's mouth.

ECD /Infant teachers **School B** has this to say:

Through dramatization, research, and educational tours will give learners firsthand experience of multiculturalism as they will be directly and actively involved. Where facilitators lack knowledge, in-service training on multicultural education, multilingual is a necessity.

ECD /Infant teachers **School C**

First and most there is a need for training in multilingual at teachers' colleges and in-service programs in multicultural education as well as attending workshops on Arts and Culture Annual events at various levels, Furthermore, multiculturalism can be successfully implemented in ECD classes through the use of games, dances, charts, and media that cater to varied cultures, dramatization, and songs

This implies that TIC are very concerned about the teaching of learners in multicultural classes with learners from diverse backgrounds at their schools. As from the responses, the administration plays a pivotal role in sanctioning educational tours and field trips so that the teachers will have adequate information about various learners' cultures that will be very useful in their day-to-day running of the classes. ECD /Infant teachers employ various strategies to implement multiculturalism. TIC school Band C concurred with ECD teacher school B on the engagement of resource- persons when it comes to some lessons on cultural practices. The resource- persons might be from those cultures represented in the class. All the ECD/ Infant teachers at Schools A, B, and C concurred that there might be effective multiculturalism if learners participate in multicultural activities, there is parental involvement, adequate training in different languages, availability of textbooks and related reading material as well as having workshops on multiculturalism. Accordingly, the study finds that TICs and facilitators have the same perceptions of what should be done to improve the effective implementation of multiculturalism. From the responses, the issue of availing resources was echoed by all the respondents. This means that such resources as textbooks are very important in the

implementation process. Furthermore, training of facilitators in multiculturalism thus looking at multilingualism was also highlighted as another aspect that if addressed will see multiculturalism effectively implemented in multicultural classes.

More so, parents need to be involved as parental involvement stands out to be considered as parents should also be taken on board what their children will be learning. This will assist to have a change of mindset towards different cultures straight from home. This is supported by Green in Zembere and Madenga (2023) that children are born into cultural systems that socialize them into accepted members of society, thus the aspect of cultural socialization will act as a source of acquiring indigenous knowledge and transmission of family and societal norms, values, behaviors and attitudes that the society expects to be normal.

Still, on the positive side, the researchers noted that teachers who can successfully navigate the diverse cultural backgrounds of their students often report increased job satisfaction, increased student engagement, and improved student achievement. Additionally, teaching a multicultural class can provide invaluable lessons in cultural understanding, empathy, and acceptance. However, Karanikola, Katsioui & Palaiologou (2022) argue that multiculturalism is temporary and liable to change as it might work either positively or negatively. This implies that job satisfaction may be just a temporary thing in a multicultural class. On the other hand, teaching multicultural classes can be demanding and difficult. Teachers end up applying collaborative teaching and making use of such strategies like educational tours, field trips, dramas, and engaging resource- persons.

Why do educators face challenges when teaching students from multiple cultural backgrounds?

The research question that seeks to find out the challenges of teaching multicultural classes was responded to by the participants giving out varied views, whereby the TiCs blamed the teachers whom they say do have a negative attitude towards certain minority cultures and lack of commitment. On the other hand, the ECD teachers believe the challenges emanate from the administrators who are not supportive of availing resources and training. Some challenges highlighted by the ECD teachers include lack of availability of resources like textbooks and the internet, and lack of training was also mentioned as a drawback to successful teaching of a multicultural class. The ECD teachers concurred on the issue of scarce resources and lack of training as they had this to say:

ECD/ Infant teacher **School B** shares his sentiments as follows:

The major challenge emanates from a lack of training in handling multicultural classes, as such teachers end up being biased towards one ethnic group's culture or developing a negative attitude towards the other cultures within a class. Furthermore, where there is no training resources that should be availed, if there is a lack of resources like textbooks and the Internet for research it becomes difficult for ECD teachers to successfully execute their duties in a multicultural class.

ECD/Infant teacher **School C** had different opinions as she felt language is the most challenge in a multicultural class. She had this to say:

The most challenge is the language barrier in a multicultural class. There is a lack of training in handling monolingual learners. This lack of training emanates from teacher training colleges where I think student teachers should have trained in bilingual and multilingual in Multiculturalism as a learning component, especially in ECD where learners are much more taught in their mother language and come from

their different communities with different cultures and languages at times.

This barrier can make it difficult for learners as they need language for communication with the teacher as well as peers. This echoed well with (Runhare & Mulaudzi, 2012; Ndamba & Madzanire, 2022) argument that more needs to be done on the language and textbooks of use at ECD level as language can ponder a lot of problems where there is no single mother language from learners. Lack of training and resources in multiculturalism was noted to be an obstacle towards effective teaching a multicultural class. Papadopoulou, Palaiologou & Karanikola (2022) maintains that teachers should constantly attend workshops and teacher- training programs which respond to their needs. In this context the issue of multiculturalism program needs staff development and workshops for facilitators to effectively implement the educational. Teachers will need to learn to manage a wide range of cultural expectations and norms, as well as potential language barriers. Additionally, teaching multicultural classes often requires teachers to be flexible and adaptable, as they must be able to adjust their teaching methods to fit the different needs and learning styles of their students. It was also noted that teachers must be prepared to confront and address issues of bias and discrimination that may arise in the classroom. As suggested by the findings in this study, parental involvement is another strategy that is being used.

Conclusion

The research on the successes and challenges of teaching multicultural classes revealed that teachers have to be willing to adapt to different student needs and be open to incorporating different cultures into their classrooms. By doing so, teachers can create a positive learning environment that helps to foster a sense of mutual respect and collaboration between students of different backgrounds. Furthermore, teachers must be aware of potential cultural misunderstandings and adjust their teaching methods to ensure that all students are included. It has also identified several challenges, such as the need for teachers to be prepared to address multicultural issues, the lack of resources for multicultural education, and the difficulty of managing and engaging with diverse student perspectives. While teaching multicultural classes can be challenging, it can also be immensely rewarding as it provides students with an opportunity to learn about and appreciate different cultures.

On the positive side, it has been found that teaching multicultural classes can be beneficial for student's academic performance, help to foster a sense of belonging and community, and offer opportunities for meaningful cross-cultural exchange. Ultimately, the research has concluded that although teaching multicultural classes can be a rewarding experience, it requires a considerable investment of time and effort to ensure that all students are supported and included.

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